

DATA GRAVITY IN MULTI-CLOUD: STRATEGIES FOR AI-POWERED DATA PLACEMENT AND RETRIEVAL

Nandakumar Ramachandran Pezhery

Xoriant Inc., USA

ABSTRACT

This paper seeks to examine how artificial intelligence (AI) can help organizations avoid the pitfalls of data gravity issues for organizations using multi-cloud systems. AI, thus can help in efficient placement and retrieval of data, improving system performance as well as achieving low latency across different cloud platforms. The examine concerns AI-based approaches for optimising data management, maintaining business operations and mitigating risks and compliance in the multi-cloud environment. The results show how technology Lid organizations are able to handle differentiation data better than it used, promoting adaptability, compatibility and utilization. Lastly, AI becomes a critical game-changer in the modern multi-cloud data management for enterprises.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, multi cloud, data gravity, data location

Cite this Article: Ramachandran Pezhery, N. (2024). Data Gravity in Multi-Cloud Strategies for AI-Powered Data Placement and Retrieval. *International Journal of Computer Engineering and Technology*, 15(6), 845–853.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJCET/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_6/IJCET_15_06_070.pdf

I. INTRODUCTION

The diffusion of cloud computing has dramatically transformed the ways firms address the distribution, storage, and processing of data. As the dependence on cloud solutions escalates, the use of multiple clouds as a major operational model is becoming more popular because each cloud offers a specific benefit. The concept of multi-cloud helps the organization to avoid dependency on any single cloud provider, provides increased fail-overs and uses optimization schemes to distribute loads between different cloud providers [1]. However, managing data at multiple cloud places poses its own number of challenges, especially about data gravity where organizations experience the inertial force that attracts data to one place causing performance issues such as latency and data retrieval. Due to the growth in usage of data consuming

applications and services within organizations, management of data across multiple cloud providers has now become an important factor for improving system capabilities.

AI with its computing power and analytical capabilities to take decisions provides a revolutionary tool to these challenges. Implemented into the cloud, machine learning algorithms allow AI to pre-emptively predict, automate, and optimize data storage and recoveries in other clouds [2]. The approach demonstrated in this paper is based on AI and not only helps to mitigate data gravity problems but can help to get the full value of multi-cloud systems. The nature of data processing will become more decentralised, and thus AI, as an orchestration tool for modern cloud environments, will play a critical role in delivering the competitive advantage, both in terms of performance and efficiency.

This research paper aims thus at analysing how the use of AI can prove helpful in dealing with issues of data gravity within multi-cloud settings and, consequently, improving system performance. It focuses on the AI approaches to decision making about data storage, data access speed, and other challenges associated with data control across numerous applications [3]. The paper also looks into the ways that AI can be applied in decision making for the management of data with a view of helping business adapt to changes in cloud service's needs.

Additionally, this paper explores how AI manages multi-cloud security and compliance dilemma making it easier to operationalize data management, security policies, and regulatory standards when working with multiple clouds. The call for true multi-cloud versatility creates the need for AI tools to flexibly orchestrate data accordingly, to support business continuity and mitigate security threats supra, as well as to always have data at the right place and under the right conditions.

To sum up, the future of the multi-cloud system may be only in AI. Through optimization of data inputs and outputs, increasing speed and security, AI is powering the new age intelligent cloud infrastructure for business.

II. DATA GRAVITY IN MULTI-CLOUD ENVIRONMENTS

Data gravity can be explained as the tendency of data to attract all the required computational resources needed to support processing, storage and analysis. In multi-cloud environment, this becomes a major issue. Issues that crop up in implementing any form of technology solution gains a whole new level of difficulty in multi-cloud environments. When applications and services, which organizations are gradually moving to different cloud providers, start accumulating data in one place, this results in poor efficiency, higher latencies, and higher expenses [4]. As soon as a significant amount of data is put into a cloud environment data processing and analysis must often remain within the same cloud provider to avoid decreased performance and extra costs due to data migration across clouds.

In situations where data is spread across the multiple cloud services, it is even worse by the fact that data gravity increases significantly. The transfer of data from one cloud or between hybrid structures is very costly, not just in terms of cost of storage, but also the time it takes to transfer large sets of data. This is often causes some of the cloud resources to be idle while others end up being stretched to their limits. However, if data exists in one cloud and a computation or a service which is needed exists in another cloud, the time and bandwidth needed to transfer the data from the first cloud to the second can dramatically slow down execution times.

However, organisations that deploy multi-cloud solutions must acknowledge the fact that those environments complicate data management [5]. There needs to be certain policies on the use of data needed and how this data is to be used and secured and such policies differ depending on the platforms used today. This results in a piecemeal approach to storing and accessing data and deepens the problem of data gravity. When data becomes 'sticky' in one cloud due to storage

capacity, processing requirements, and connectivity consideration it becomes almost impossible to transfer data across clouds to the optimal resource utilization.

However, AI can assist in reducing the issues created by the data gravity. By use of machine Learning algorithms and Predictive analytics, a business can predict where data is likely to be required and hence store it in the right cloud. These AI approaches make data management more reactive hence improving computing resources usage and making it difficult for data gravity to slow down the operation of an organization [6]. AI for data orchestration can help guess the placement and subsequently transfer of data implying an optimal utilization of resources as well as a cut down on cost and delays in multi-cloud environments.

III. AI-POWERED DATA PLACEMENT AND RETRIEVAL STRATEGIES

AI-based approaches are now indispensable for managing placement and access of data across the multi-cloud setting with the issues of data gravity being among the most pressing. One of the key benefits of technologies in AI is that AI can analyse a large amount of data in real-time, and make suggestions regarding where in the system that data should be placed given parameters like workload demand, network conditions, and latency constraints. When using machine learning, AI can automatically organize data across different clouds, making sure that it is in the right cloud now and in the future.

Implementing AI into a system can enable the system to move data around according to the fluctuating workloads of the applications, and realize where the data is going to be most needed in the future [7]. For instance, AI can bring data closer to the computing resources needed for processing or analysing data which will help save time and costs incurred to move data around. It eliminates congested areas and optimizes the functional performance of the entire system. Also, AI can improve capacity of data retrieval by understanding and analysing access patterns and storing the accessed data in the nearest cloud zones [8]. As such, it becomes easier to deliver fast results with specific emphasis on the frequently required data to improve the client's experience and organization performance.

AI's ability to analyse cloud environments also makes it possible to optimize the cloud environments in real-time. As the system takes data on performance and use of resources, it is possible to shift strategies and distribute data in order to avoid buildup and a resultant slowdown of the process. This has a significant performance enhancing implication for the multi-cloud architecture and its capacity to manage workloads and the phenomenon of data gravity.

IV. AI FOR ENHANCED MULTI-CLOUD DATA EFFICIENCY

Applying artificial intelligence (AI) in order to District Multiple Cloud Data is innovating how organizations handle data in multiple cloud environments. In the multi-cloud environment, this is a situation where a business organization uses the services of several CSPs to satisfy various needs, and it may be cumbersome to control the traffic flow between these clouds [9]. However, with AI, these procedures can be made automatic for decisions about placing data, retrieving data, and optimizing data and the database system resulting to the enhancement of system efficiency, decreased latency, and decreased cosmic costs of operation.

AI can greatly improve data utilization and distribution especially in multi-cloud settings where data needs to be available on request and based on its usage frequency. Conventional approaches to handling data have been fraught with a flood of workloads to move between clouds or to tweak at the bare minimum with human interference. AI, on the other hand, can always monitor workload and decide for itself as a distributed system where data should be stored and how it should be processed [10]. For instance, machine learning applications can foresee the amounts of future data use, making it easy to pre-position data in the cloud that will

generate the most value by being accessed faster and with the lowest latency. This approach, therefore, eliminates direct data mobility across clouds, which is costly in terms of bandwidth and reduces the total system response time [11].

Another important area for the application of AI is the task of minimizing data finding time. In a multi-cloud context, data might be partitioned by regions or clouds, so getting it would require considerable latency if it would not be stored in the right place. AI has the capability to know which data is commonly used and it will then self-learn that frequently used data should be stored in the cloud so that can easily be retrieved. This minimizes latency through appropriate resource dimensions to enable the users to get to essential data in the shortest time possible. Moreover, with the continued observation of data access trends more specific approaches may be used to shift where the data is kept or even on which cloud or region to better adapt to the continually changing usage patterns. This keeps the multi-cloud architecture nimble for being able to accommodate concerns of the business.

AI when employed for multi-cloud benefit provides usage and performance analytics about data that can help businesses in decision making about cloud strategy. AI can detect some areas of inefficiency, for instance, limited usage of data storage, and suggest how best to utilize the resources. This can lead to optimization of cost since businesses only consume cloud resources dependent on their needs. Further, AI based systems also assist in better management of cloud resource by identifying and anticipating workloads and manage the resources accordingly in terms of up gradation or constriction. This agility allows companies to scale to meet an increased demand without fatally committing too much capital to the cloud.

AI also facilitates better handling and security of data and managing them securely in multi-cloud networks. AI, By capturing data across various clouds, it can give an executive summary of security threats and compliance violations in real-time. This means that through automation, data has to be stored in compliance with the set laws hence protecting the data while meeting the regulatory needs at the same time.

AI is a great opportunity to develop the methods for getting the greatest results with the given amount of data in multi-cloud setting. With respect to the placement, retrieval, and optimization of data in and across the multiple cloud platforms, AI makes it possible to ensure that data available for use is safe and properly controlled while at the same time it is efficiently utilized. Over the years, AI is expected to advance more, which will enhance the enhancements in managing the multiple clouds for the operations of businesses in improving the performance and further lower on the operation costs.

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The usage of AI techniques in multi-cloud data management has clearly pinpointed improved efficacy and productivity in reduced examples and pilot applications. The first and most significant outcome of data placement and retrieval with AI support concerns the decreased latency of data access anywhere in multiple clouds. For instance, predictive algorithms that correlated patterns of data access experience have helped organizations migrate automatically data in lock-step to cloud regions characterized by elevated latencies to more heavily usage, thereby optimizing system and overall performance.

MEASURED LATENCY BETWEEN CLOUD AND EDGE COMPUTING

Fig. 1 Latency of Cloud and Edge computing of Application and database server

The use of AI in forecasting of demand of the workload and self-provisioning of resources in various cloud environments and models has enhanced both cost control and resource management [12]. Because of AI, uncontrolled movement of data from one cloud to another has been cordoned, hence reducing costs on bandwidths and overall consumption of resources.

Cloud Service Cost Savings Reporting Dashboard

Fig. 2 Demystifying Reserved Instances: Cost Optimization in the Cloud

There are some issues that are still worth being solved – security and governance of the multi-cloud environment. As AI improves data access, data sovereignty and compliance becomes key success factors since AI involves handling of large volumes of data.

Fig. 3 Cloud and AI business

However, the constant supervision and newly emerging changes made by AI imply the possibility of achieving the appropriate balance between the degree of efficiency and the necessary compliance, making the multi-cloud structure more sustainable in the longer run [13].

VI. CONCLUSION

By leveraging AI in multi-cloud data management, data placement is improved, latency is reduced, and the cost of operation is considerably lowered. Through the utilization of predictive algorithms real-time monitoring makes sure that data is available and resources are managed across multiple cloud platforms. Security and compliance issues still linger, however, by unravelling the potentials of Ainhum in multi-cloud settings, it paves way for new multifaceted solutions to harness the unmatched potential of multi cloud infrastructures to support today's modern businesses today's modern business landscape.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abdel-Rahman, M., & Younis, F. A. (2022). Developing an Architecture for Scalable Analytics in a Multi-Cloud Environment for Big Data-Driven Applications. *International Journal of Business Intelligence and Big Data Analytics*, 5(1), 66-73. <https://research.tensorgate.org/index.php/IJBIBDA/article/view/78>
- [2] Rashid, M. N., Abed, L. H., & Awad, W. K. (2022). Financial information security using hybrid encryption technique on multi-cloud architecture. *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, 11(6), 3450-3461. <https://doi.org/10.11591/eei.v11i6.3967>
- [3] George, A. S. (2024). The Cloud Comedown: Understanding the Emerging Trend of Cloud Exit Strategies. *Partners Universal International Innovation Journal*, 2(5), 1-32. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13993933>
- [4] Schlicker, M. Multicloud Infrastructure Broker for Edge Orchestration Framework. https://www.nitindermohan.com/documents/student-thesis/MichaelSchlicker_MT.pdf
- [5] Pandey, A. (2022). Trusted Resource Allocation in Volunteer Edge-Cloud Computing for Scientific Applications (Doctoral dissertation, University of Missouri-Columbia). <https://www.proquest.com/openview/d19d62d0b13e5ff35409de693b549a7b/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>
- [6] Trivedi, A. (2024). Autoscaling for Cost Efficiency in Cloud Services. *International Journal of Research Radicals in Multidisciplinary Fields*, ISSN: 2960-043X, 3(2), 143-155. <https://www.researchradicals.com/index.php/rr/article/view/114>
- [7] Sharma, S., & Chaturvedi, R. (2021). Optimizing Scalability and Performance in Cloud Services: Strategies and Solutions. *ESP Journal of Engineering & Technology Advancements (ESP JETA)*, 1(2), 116-133. <https://espjeta.org/Volume1-Issue2/JETA-V1I2P115.pdf>
- [8] Marino, J., & Risso, F. (2023). Is the Computing Continuum Already Here?. arXiv preprint arXiv:2309.09822. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2309.09822>
- [9] Kortelainen, O. (2023). Infrastructure management in multicloud environments (Master's thesis). <https://urn.fi/URN:NBN:fi:tuni-202304254451>
- [10] Adekanmbi, A., Andrews, M., Oladapo, D., & Spencer, D. Cyber Forensic Tools and Techniques Used in Cloud Computing. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Aishat-Adekanmbi/publication/379021926_Cyber_Forensic_Tools_and_Techniques_Used_in

_Cloud_Computing/links/65f5d6ffc05fd268801ae48c/Cyber-Forensic-Tools-and-Techniques-Used-in-Cloud-Computing.pdf

- [11] Alonso, J., Orue-Echevarria, L., & Huarte, M. (2022). CloudOps: Towards the operationalization of the cloud continuum: Concepts, challenges and a reference framework. *Applied Sciences*, 12(9), 4347. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12094347>
- [12] Nambiar, A., & Mundra, D. (2022). An overview of data warehouse and data lake in modern enterprise data management. *Big data and cognitive computing*, 6(4), 132. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bdcc6040132>
- [13] Harauzek, D. (2022). Cloud Computing: Challenges of cloud computing from business users perspective-vendor lock-in. <https://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:lnu:diva-115089>

Citation: Ramachandran Pezhery, N. (2024). Data Gravity in Multi-Cloud Strategies for AI-Powered Data Placement and Retrieval. *International Journal of Computer Engineering and Technology*, 15(6), 845–853.

Abstract Link: https://iaeme.com/Home/article_id/IJCET_15_06_070

Article Link:

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJCET/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_6/IJCET_15_06_070.pdf

Copyright: © 2024 Authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

This work is licensed under a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)**.

✉ editor@iaeme.com